

THE IMPACT OF NON-INTEREST INCOME ON THE NET NON-INTEREST MARGIN IN THE CONDITIONS OF SHARP CURRENCY FLUCTUATIONS AND THE TREND OF GEL DEVALUATION

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Abstract

Non-interest income is an important source of revenue for financial institutions. It speaks of earnings derived from sources other than interest on loans and deposits. Fees, commissions, profits from the sale of securities, and other forms of revenue fall under this category. In this study, we'll look at non-interest income's significance, its causes, and how it affects the financial performance of the banking industry based on the Georgian example. Given research will analyze the dynamics of possible currency speculation behavior of the banking system, especially in the conditions of sharp currency fluctuations and the trend of devaluation of the local currency. A specific role is devoted to currency speculations using foreign exchange operations, using open positions of net assets (long position) or net liabilities (short position) in foreign currency. It is based on conscious calculations based on the expectation of the future price of the foreign currency. The comparative analysis method is used for the analysis and evaluations.

Keywords: Banking, Georgi, Non-interest Income, Currency Fluctuation

Introduction

We explain that the profit or loss from conversion operations is the net gain from the purchase and sale of currency, and the revaluation of foreign currency funds depends on the exchange rate. As a rule, the result of buying and selling currency is positive, due to the positive margin of buying and selling, on the other hand, the result of the revaluation of currency funds is negative, especially for the devaluation trend of local currencies, because it is calculated in relation to the pre-reporting period. Exchange rate differences that arise in the settlement of monetary items, or in the translation of monetary items at an exchange rate that is different from the exchange rate at the time of initial recognition in the current period, or from the exchange rate used for translation in the financial statements of the previous period, should be recognized in profit or loss in the reporting period in which they arise.

Transactions made in foreign currency at the time of initial recognition must be reflected in the working currency, according to the spot exchange rate between the working currency and the given foreign currency on the day of the transaction. The date of operation is when this operation is first classified for recognition per international financial reporting standards. In practice, they often use the exchange rate close to the current exchange rate at the time of the operation. For example, the average exchange rate of the week or month can be used for all operations performed in a given period

Accordingly, if the foreign exchange funds in the settlement period will be more than the previous period, i.e. its balance sheet value will be higher, it will be revalued in profit, and vice versa in loss.

Historically, on the trend of devaluation of the GEL against the US dollar, the profit from conversion operations increases, and its growth dynamics depend on the amplitude of the fluctuation.

The purpose of determining the limit of the total open foreign exchange position of the National Bank of

Georgia is to reduce the possible risk in the event of a change in the foreign currency exchange rate as a result of performing foreign exchange operations because such a change can negatively affect the profit, capital, liquidity, and solvency of commercial banks. Foreign exchange position is the difference between a bank's assets and liabilities denominated in foreign currency.

The foreign currency position can be closed or open: a) the foreign currency position is closed when the amounts of the bank's assets and liabilities according to the types of foreign currency are equal to each other; b) The foreign currency position is open when the amounts of the bank's assets and liabilities according to the types of foreign currency are not equal to each other. On the other hand, an open currency position is long when the bank's assets in the same type of foreign currency are greater than its liabilities; And the open currency position is short when the bank's assets in the same type of foreign currency are less than its liabilities;

The total open currency position is the largest among the sum of long open currency positions and the sum of short open currency positions of the bank according to all foreign currencies. Foreign currency contracts include obligations under spot, futures, forward, and swap contracts for buying or selling foreign currency, and rights and obligations stipulated by options in monetary volumes.

In addition, during the calculation of the bank's overall open foreign exchange position, the largest of the sum of the long open foreign exchange positions and the sum of the short open foreign exchange positions in the bank's balance sheet and off-balance sheet statements for all foreign currencies shall be taken, which should not exceed 20 percent of the bank's supervisory capital (NBG, 2022).

Bank speculation is distinguished by high volatility, which contributes to the strengthening of chaos in the economy. However, until the economy is

out of balance and out of control, speculators go unnoticed. Speculators are considered to be all those who open a position in foreign currency, regardless of their motive and the expected exchange rate change in the future. According to international practice, the foreign exchange market allows currency trading by both "speculators" and hedgers, since there is no possibility of strict differentiation of these two categories of foreign exchange market participants.

This applies to Georgian banks, especially large systematic banks, which practically represent a foreign exchange by the size of their assets, despite the restrictions imposed by the National Bank, which are imposed according to the requirements of the rules for establishing, calculating, and protecting the limit of the general open foreign exchange position of commercial banks, they can speculate in foreign exchange with high-profit interest. Both by opening a long position, that is, by accumulating US dollars, counting on the depreciation of the GEL in the future, as well as by opening a short currency position, counting on the strengthening of the GEL in the future, for example, by playing on the sale of currency futures contracts (forward, option, swap). In addition, during high fluctuations, the demand for foreign currency based on negative expectations increases, which increases the trend of devaluation of the GEL and therefore prolongs the correction period.

2014-2015 and 2018-2019 years were taken as the research period when currency fluctuations were relatively high and the exchange rate of the lari against the US dollar was characterized by high volatility. The research is based on official statistics of the National Bank of Georgia and financial reporting forms of banks.

Literature review

Financial institutions depend heavily on non-interest income as a source of income, especially in the present context of low-interest rates and heightened competition. Fees for services including account upkeep, ATM use, credit card processing, asset management, Fintech services (Gamsakhurdia, Koki-auri, 2021; Lashkhi, 2022; Lashkhi et al, 2022), and advisory services are just a few of the ways that banks get non-interest income.

Banks' revenue sources are diversified by non-interest income, which reduces the risk associated with depending primarily on interest income. For instance, Belew et al.'s (2018) study discovered that Nigerian banks of all sizes produced greater non-interest revenue than banks of all sizes.

Non-interest income was important to the banking sector in 2015, as evidenced by the fact that it made up 36.6% of the total revenue of Chinese commercial banks, according to research by Chen et al. (2018). Similarly, to this, research by Gul et al. (2020) discovered that non-interest income accounted for 34% of Pakistani commercial banks' overall revenue in 2017 year. The banking sector in Georgia has also been significantly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, also called a Coronomic crisis (Charaia, Papava, 2022), notably in terms of non-interest revenue. The overall non-interest revenue of Georgian commercial banks

declined 10.4% in 2020 compared to 2019 according to research done by the National Bank of Georgia (NBG, 2021). The survey also discovered that commission and fee income will be 15.4% lower in 2020 than it was in 2019.

Kapanadze & Kekelidze, also, Jorbenadze & Bregvadze (2021) studies examine the determinants of non-interest income in Georgian commercial banks using data from 2013 to 2018. The results show that bank size, diversification of banking activities, and operating efficiency are significant determinants of non-interest income. Based on similar findings Javakhadze & Imnaishvili, (2021) suggest that banks should focus on developing new products and services, such as digital banking, to increase non-interest income.

The effect of non-interest income on financial performance has been the subject of several research. Return on assets (ROA), which is derived by dividing net income by total assets, is one of the most widely used metrics of financial success. Return on equity (ROE), which is computed by dividing net income by total equity, is another indicator of financial performance.

According to studies, non-interest income and financial success are positively correlated. Profitability as determined by ROA and ROE has been found to be significantly impacted, in particular, by non-interest income. For instance, research conducted in 2013 by Ongore and Kusa discovered that non-interest revenue significantly improved the profitability of Kenyan commercial banks. Should be mentioned that the COVID-19 pandemic had its impact also on this particular issue too. Hasko et al. (2021) based on 51 banks in Europe (a study based on the time period of January - September 2020) revealed a 10% loss in non-interest revenue compared to the same time in 2019 was primarily brought on by a drop in trading and fee-based income. The effect on financial performance was minimal, though, because banks could rely on government assistance and liquidity infusions. The authors also discovered that smaller and less diversified banks saw a greater degree of NII reduction.

Osuji et al. (2021) show that the pandemic played a crucial role also emerging countries, based on research from 65 banks (January - June 2020), it had a significant effect on both interest income and non-interest income, although NII was more severely affected. While revenue from other sources, such as insurance and investment services, remained mostly consistent, the reduction in NII was primarily caused by a decline in fee-based income and trading income.

A specific example from Uzuner et al. (2021) analyzing Turkish example, based on 15 local banks (January - September 2020), shows that the pandemic had a detrimental effect on non-interest income, which fell by 8.5% compared to the same time in 2019. The primary factor, which was responsible for nearly 70% of the loss, was a decline in fee-based income. However, throughout the epidemic, revenue from credit card operations and insurance services surged.

Analysis of non-interest income of commercial banks in Georgia

Despite the open foreign exchange position limits, large international banks are still able to engage in foreign exchange speculation, especially in derivatives trading, by playing on the open foreign exchange position margin. For example, they open a long foreign exchange position and acquire foreign currency assets, closing the positions in the future at a rate that is already profitable for them. A clear example of this was the example of the famous British bank Berings in the 90s of the last century, when the bank traded derivatives and collected foreign exchange contracts on the Tokyo exchange with the possibility of their future appreciation, it went bankrupt due to pure force majeure. If not for the famous Kobe earthquake in Japan, which caused the price of foreign exchange contracts to fall, it burned in time and had to close all contracts at unprofitable prices, and the loss consumed the entire capital of the bank.

It should be noted that in the part of the non-interest income of the leading Georgian commercial banks, there is a record increase in the profit from conversion operations, that is, from the purchase and sale of currency (NBG, 2023c).

It is significant that compared to the same period of 2018, the profit from conversion operations has increased from 200.8 million GEL to 354.5 million GEL, i.e. by 154 million GEL, and in percentage terms, it has increased by a record 77%, i.e. by almost 2/3. But,

most interestingly, in what period is this growth observed? The banking sector received the highest net profit from conversion operations in July 2019 - 70.7 million GEL, which is an absolute record in recent years. Also in August - 46.9 million GEL, and in September - 49 million. Lari. In fact, in just 3 months, the net profit of the banking sector from conversion operations amounted to 167 million GEL, which exceeds even the figure for the first 9 months of last year's profit (155 million GEL). (see Diagram 1)

The most interesting thing in these statistics is that these months, especially July-August, are characterized by the highest fluctuations of the lari, which was largely related to the events of June 20-21, 2019, because the next trend of the devaluation of the lari was due to these revolutionary events and negative expectations. It started on June 25 (NBG, 2023b).

According to the months, in July, not only the income from conversion operations increased significantly, but also its contribution to the net profit rose to a historical maximum and amounted to 86% (Diagram 1), while even in June its rate was one of the lowest in recent years and was 10%. did not exceed What is no less important, the largest part of this profit, 75%, falls on the two leading system-forming banks, namely TBC Bank, and Bank of Georgia (NBG, 2023d).

Diagram 1. Income from conversion operation in the Georgian banking system

It can be seen from this that in a revolutionary situation when negative expectations increase. In order to ensure currency risks, requests from legal and natural persons for currency purchase and sale operations and conversions, both in terms of trade operations and servicing of loans taken in foreign currency, are increasing significantly.

In addition, the increase in the profits of banks is also due to the fact that if in stable situations the interest margin between the purchase and sale price of currency does not exceed 1-3 whites, during high currency

fluctuations, along with the increase in the volume of foreign exchange operations, the margin increases even to 5-7 whites. This fact is in line with the expert assessments, according to which the devaluation of the lari and the chaos are arranged by the big banks and they are largely interested in it and less by individual companies, especially in the conditions of the dominance of two banks in the market and the lack of transparency of the "Bloomberg" trading system, currency speculations are also not excluded.

Diagram 2. Net income from conversion and currency exchange operations in Georgia

The relationship between the conversion operations and the profit/loss obtained from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds and the dynamics of the exchange rate is very interesting for analysis. This relationship becomes especially correlated during periods before and during currency fluctuations. In particular, the correlation has the character of a kind of "pit" of a sharply expressed asymmetric graph, when the profits from conversion operations increase sharply, and the losses from the

revaluation of foreign exchange funds also increase sharply. In other relatively stable periods, but during not sharp fluctuations in the devaluation of the GEL, the profits from conversion operations are not high, as well as the losses arising from the revaluation of foreign exchange operations are relatively low. At the same time, in the conditions of the relative strengthening of the GEL, the result obtained from exchange operations and the profit obtained from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds are also positive.

Diagram 3. Average monthly exchange rate, USD/GEL

As can be seen from Diagram 2 and Diagram 3, in the period of 2012-2019 between these two graphs, a pronounced asymmetric shape in terms of profit and

loss was recorded in 2015 during the impact of external shocks and in March-April 2016 and January-February 2018 during the next devaluation trend of lari.

Diagram 4. Indicators of the banking system 2018-2019

In our opinion, the January-December figures of 2018-2019 also give a very interesting picture. The graph shows that in June 2019, the trend changed and the profit from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds broke the year's record and amounted to 17,739 million GEL, while Roder had a loss in the previous months, while the profit from conversion operations was recorded at the lowest level during the year - 3,315 million GEL. (Chart 4)

On the contrary, already in July 2019, when the new trend of devaluation of the Gel started, the profit of the system from conversion operations reached a record level and amounted to 70.69 million GEL, while the loss from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds also reached a record level - 33.8 million GEL. This trend continued in August-September as well, which generated a record profit from conversion operations of 166 million GEL in these three months, and on the other hand, a record loss from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds - 67 million GEL. The asymmetry of the trend in June, which was reflected in a peculiar loop, and the sharply changed trend in the following months raise doubts about currency speculation or playing at the maximum limit of the open currency position.

From this point of view, the month of October is also very interesting, when there was a sharp change in the trend of the previous period, exactly similar to the month of June when the profit from conversion operations rose again to the highest mark since July and amounted to 51 million GEL, while the loss from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds was also recorded at a high of 23 million GEL.

The month of October is significant from the point of view that it was in October that the National Bank lowered the reserve ratio on funds raised in foreign currency by 5%, which should have caused the foreign currency to enter the market up to 700 million US dollars and generally strengthen the GEL. From the graph of the exchange rate of GEL against the US dollar, it can be seen that the monetary effect of the reservation did not work practically. Couldn't influence the exchange rate on the market due to the fact that banks continue to buy US dollars despite the stimulus to supply the dollar supply!

Most importantly, the increase in refinancing loans was recorded in October 2019 (NBG, 2023a), when instead of decreasing as a rule, it increased from 2,050,000,000 GEL to a record 2,350,000,000 GEL! (Diagram 5)

Diagram 5. The volume of refinancing loans in 2017 -2019

To evaluate the analysis of the system, we used a comparative analysis of the non-interest income of the leading 6 Georgian banks in the first 3 quarters. The analysis is performed based on the data of the National Bank, for those system banks whose assets exceed 1 billion GEL and make up 92% of the entire system.

Along with the two leading banks (TBC Bank, and Bank of Georgia), which own 73% of the system, the financial results of Liberty Bank, Kartu Bank, Base Bank, and VTB Bank are also included in the study. (Diagram 6)

Diagram 6. Financial Results of the Georgian Banks for 2017-2019 Years

It can be seen from the presented graph that in the second quarter, all banks had losses from the revaluation of foreign exchange operations, except for TBC Bank. In addition, it is TBC Bank that has a significant influence on the trend of the system in the month of June, according to which, as we have seen, the conversion profit and the high rate of profit from

the revaluation of foreign exchange funds. Also, according to the 3rd quarter, TBC repeats the trend indicators recorded by the system in July-September, which is reflected in the record conversion profit and also the record loss received from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds.

Diagram 7. The results of the two systemic banks for 2018-2019 years

From the presented graphs, it can be seen that of the two largest system-forming banks of the country, which constitute 74% of system assets, TBC Bank practically repeats the systemic trend in 2018-2019, especially in May-November 2019.

in October, when it reached the historical maximum of 7,143 million GEL, if not in 2019, and the profitability was maintained even in November-December. In October, it is important to the extent that the amount released on the market with the reduction of the reserve norm by 5% practically did not affect the exchange rate.

It is worth noting that since June, the income from Nostro accounts has increased significantly, especially

Diagram 8. Earnings from Nostro accounts, 2019

Net interest income

In the case of high fluctuations and currency devaluation, if it has a medium-term nature, due to the high dollarization of loans, banks' interest incomes also increase namely net interest income.

Diagram 9. Interest Income and Expenses in Georgia

As can be seen in Diagram 9, after decreasing in June 2019 compared to May, the interest income started to increase from July, Khdolo reached a record quarterly rate in October-December - 976.6 million GEL, which is 27% of the total annual interest income.

Similarly, net interest income as of the 4th quarter amounted to 490.9 million GEL, which was 27% of the total net interest income.

The trend of 2014-2015 also gives a very interesting picture (Diagram 10).

Diagram 10. Indicators of the banking system 2014-2015

Our foreign exchange market has a very small volume, and at the same time, the weather in the interbank foreign exchange market is created by 4-5 banks, and to a large extent by 2 banks, which is why the probability of informal influences on the market is quite high. More than 10 billion dollars of foreign exchange transactions are made on the foreign exchange market every year, although the exchange rate of lari is set only according to interbank foreign exchange market transactions, which do not exceed 1 billion dollars annually.

In 2014, the transactions concluded in the interbank market, including the interventions of the National Bank, amounted to 904 million dollars, that is, the exchange rate of the GEL was determined by transactions of this volume, while in the foreign exchange market in 2014 transactions of more than 13 billion dollars were concluded. This practically means that the exchange rate of GEL is determined not by the market and the economy, but by 2 large banks, with small-volume transactions. Banks trade with each other, on average, up to 100 million dollars per month, as a result of which the exchange rate of the lari is set, and with this exchange rate, more than a billion dollars of currency transactions are made every month. In addition, up to 75% of the total turnover of the interbank foreign exchange market comes to only 5 banks, and from this, it can be seen that there is a high risk that, in addition to operating at the limit of the open foreign exchange position, speculative transactions also take place.

Banks have the leverage and the opportunity to "regulate" the exchange rate of the GEL with transactions worth up to a billion dollars every year, and then, at this rate, to conclude foreign exchange transactions with individuals and legal entities, in total, up to 7 billion.

This is precisely the asymmetric system when the interbank foreign exchange market is not the real determinant of the economy's supply and demand for foreign currency. A number of experts have suggested that the fluctuation of the exchange rate of the lari is part of a far-reaching and well-planned policy. Unfortunately, the actions of the National Bank are often delayed and even today they remind us of the period of Kadagidze, when his individual statements, instead of neutralizing negative expectations, artificially sowed panic in the society.

Unfortunately, during that period, a rather difficult situation was created regarding the exchange rate of the lari in Georgia, which started as early as November 2014. This problem, first of all, causes a lot of damage to the economy, as well as to socially vulnerable, low, and middle classes. In 2014-15, SEB had more than enough reserve money - 3 billion dollars, of which it spent only 200 million dollars. Regulator took 120 million dollars out of 200 million dollars only when there was already panic in the country. For example, we can compare the years 2009 and 2014. In 2009, when the exchange rate of the lari was stable, the National Bank of Georgia provided 112 million dollars to the market, thus practically holding the exchange rate.

Instead, in 2014, when the exchange rate changed significantly, it spent only 100 million dollars. According to the data of the periods of funds spent by the National Bank in 2014, it is clear how SEB does not interfere consciously in the processes in order to maintain the stability of the GEL exchange rate. If in 2009 the National Bank intervened in the foreign exchange market 53 times and thereby maintained stability, in 2014 it intervened only 18 times. Its deliberate action also affects refinanced loans. If until 2013 the maximum loan was 300 million GEL, in 2014, when the exchange rate of the GEL was falling, the National Bank increased it to the historical maximum – of 700 million GEL.

Since August 2014, both positions have been profitable, the profit from conversion operations and the profit from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds, and in December, the record profit was fixed by the sum of both these positions. Moreover, since November 2014, the profit from the revaluation of foreign currency exceeds the profit from conversion operations, and in December-January, this trend goes into asymmetry twice. In particular, with a record rate of conversion profit in December, and January 2015 compared to 2014, it was already in the form of profit from the revaluation of foreign exchange funds and instead, in the form of loss from conversion operations.

In this case, TBC Bank practically repeats the nature of the systemic trend. As for the Bank of Georgia, its trend in December 2014 and January 2015 coincides with TBC Bank, instead, in February-March, it reached a record profit in the revaluation of foreign exchange funds. On the other hand, the loss from conversion operations is also high.

Conclusion

Based on the fact that in June 2019, the banking system had a low index in conversion operations, and a high profit in currency revaluation correlates with the data of TBC Bank in this period, which indicates that the bank purchased dollars at a high price, that is, it traded with a lower margin than the average system and deliberately went for a loss, Instead, he won the revaluation.

Instead, already in the 3rd quarter, the bank used the negative impact of the revolutionary situation that developed since the end of June on the foreign exchange market, it started to contribute conversion profits, i.e., to play on the artificial devaluation of the exchange rate, which was naturally reflected in the loss of currency revaluation.

True, in October the bank lost in conversion and won in revaluation, similar to June. The fact that the bank followed this strategy is confirmed by the dynamics of the exchange rate and especially the record-high increase in refinancing loans, along with the increased profit from Nostro accounts, the leading operator of which, based on its market share, is TBC Bank. This largely resulted in virtually zero effect of the reduction in reserves on the foreign exchange market.

The financial results obtained from the currency devaluation at the end of 2014 and the first half of 2015 should be evaluated in the same way, both on the

example of TBC Bank and the second largest bank - "Bank of Georgia".

Therefore, it can be seen that, in certain periods, banks focus on long currency positions, that is, they collect foreign currency, while they close the open currency position at a profitable rate for them in the future.

Today, the size of the capital of these two banks allows them to freely operate at the limit of the open currency position, especially since these banks actually represent their own currency exchanges, and it is possible that they use the Bloomberg system to fix the desired exchange rate.

Large banks did not lose anything due to currency devaluation, on the contrary, they made record profits, both in terms of profit from conversion operations and net interest income, that is, they practically covered the losses arising from currency revaluation.

The instability and unpredictability of the exchange rate, first of all, have a negative effect on Georgian business, because as a result of the aforementioned positioning of the leading Georgian banks, business operating costs increase, which reduces their competitiveness, which again affects consumers negatively by increasing prices.

Therefore, it becomes one of the additional factors of negative impact on inflation.

It is true, from the point of view of de-dollarization, the National Bank has taken important steps in recent years, reduced dollarization and which means limiting lending in foreign currency to uninsured borrowers, requesting information from credit bureaus about all loans in terms of individual currencies, and requiring banks to routinely assess currency risks. But dollarized deposits remain a problem, which in turn leads to the dollarization of loans.

High levels of foreign currency-denominated deposits cause banks to lend to local borrowers in foreign currencies to maintain balanced balance sheet positions while shifting the exchange rate burden from banks to depositors. On the other hand, important factors causing the dollarization of deposits are the inflation rate and volatility, as well as currency devaluation in low-income countries. And the asymmetric exchange rate policy encourages depositors to keep their deposits mostly in foreign currency in order to maintain their purchasing power.

In addition, in countries with dollarized and highly import-dependent economies, interest rates and their differences are high, resulting from risks arising from currency devaluation. Consequently, price elasticity to monetary and credit shocks is often higher in countries with dollarized economies, because inflation is more responsive to monetary and credit shocks due to weak policy transmission mechanisms.

In the conditions of an oligopolistic market, where the assets of two banks are up to 75% of the total banking assets, the SEB is obliged to intervene more actively in the market for the sake of macroeconomic stabilization and limit the profits of the banks, both in the direction of increasing the refinancing rate, interest margin and interventions in the market.

In terms of de-dollarization and increasing the attractiveness of the local currency, it is necessary, especially in the short term, to focus on measures that will make the local currency more attractive and reduce the asymmetry of the exchange rate policy and, therefore, the probability of currency speculation.

From the point of view of de-dollarization of deposits and credits, it will be important to develop the liquid capital market in local currency in the medium term, along with the development of the stock market in the long term, which will help to reduce the level of dollarization of credits along with the de-dollarization of deposits.

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